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Impact Of Human Resource Development On Academic Staff Job Performance In Public Universities In Benue State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated impact of human resource development on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State. Two research questions guided the study. Two hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The research design for the study was the ex post facto survey design. The population of the study comprised 2,042 academic staff in three public universities in Benue State. The sample was 355 representing 17.38% of the total population. A researcher developed questionnaire titled “Human Resource Development and Academic Staff Job Performance Questionnaire (HRDASJPQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, two in Educational Management, Department of Educational Foundations and one in Mathematics Education in the Department of Science and Mathematics Education from the Faculty of Education, Rev. Fr. Moses Orshio Adasu University, Makurdi. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained through a trial-test which yielded a Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.91. Data were analysed using Mean (\bar{x}) and Standard Deviation (σ) to answer the research questions and Chi-square (χ^2) test of goodness-of-fit to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that mentoring and managerial coaching has significant positive impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that human resource development has significant positive significant impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made among others: that the Ministry of Education should prioritize the implementation and support of structured mentoring programmes in public universities, recognizing that mentoring has a significant positive impact on academic staff job performance by enhancing teaching effectiveness, research output and supervisory competence.

Keywords: human resource development, mentoring, managerial coaching and academic staff job performance

INTRODUCTION

There appears to be growing global concern over the job performance of academic staff in public universities, largely due to increasing workloads, performance-based evaluation systems, job insecurity, and the pressure to publish. These factors have collectively affected teaching quality, research productivity, and the overall well-being of academic staff (Shin & Jung, 2019). In Finland, despite having

a well-funded and highly ranked higher education system, studies reveal rising levels of anxiety among academic staff, largely associated with fixed-term contracts, intense competition for research funding, and heightened performance measurement systems. These conditions have raised concerns about long-term motivation and the sustainability of academic staff job performance (Pekkola & Siekkinen, 2020). Across West Africa, particularly in Nigeria, persistent challenges such as poor remuneration, irregular promotion practices, frequent industrial actions, and inadequate teaching and research facilities have heightened concerns about declining academic staff job performance in public universities (Adeniyi & Ojo, 2022). Within North-Central Nigeria, especially in Benue State, these national and regional challenges appear even more pronounced, as public universities face severe funding shortages, overcrowded classrooms, and limited opportunities for professional development. These conditions raise serious concerns about the ability of academic staff to sustain optimal job performance (Terfa & Igbudu, 2019).

Performance refers to the work-related behavior, academic staff exhibit in discharging their assigned duties in organizations. It involves certain behaviours expected by an organization for academic staff to exhibit (Liu & Liu, 2022). Furthermore, Chukwuma, Agbaru, Agbo and Ezenwa, (2022) view the indicators of performance as the quality of output, the quantity of output, the timeliness of output, and the productivity of labour. Academic staff job performance is seen as the degree to which an organizational member contributes to achieving the goals of the organization (Chukwuma et al, 2022). Asfiah, Twumasi, Sarpong and Darko, (2022) defined performance as the actual behaviour displayed by each individual as a result of his role in the company. According to Attahiru (2021), academic staff job performance is seen as the value added to the existing effort of the academic staff in terms of quantity, quality, efficiency, and effectiveness, whereas related behaviour can be categorized according to the level of loyalty in contributing to the increase in value added.

Academic staff job performance is achieving and accomplishing specific and well-determined tasks in the organization, these tasks will be measured with well-planned and predefined goals, objectives (Safitri & Lathifah, 2019). Armstrong (2020), stated that Academic staff job Performance management is the continuous process of improving performance by setting individual and team goals that are aligned to the strategic goals of the organization, planning performance to achieve the goals, reviewing and assessing progress, and developing the knowledge, skills, and abilities of people (Armstrong, 2020). Some of the main performance measurements are productivity, efficiency, effectiveness, quality and profitability (Armstrong, 2020). Academic staff job performance demonstrates the improvement in production by perfect use of new technology with the help of highly aggravated academic staff (Al- Omari, Alomari & Aljawarneh, 2020). Managers usually set high standards for individual in order to measure the performance of academic staff for the betterment of organization (Buchanan. & Badham, 2020). Effective human resource development could enhance academic staff skills, knowledge, and motivation, leading to improved job performance and productivity in public universities.

Human Resource Development is a key component of human resource management. According to Vulpen (2016), effective Human Resource Management encompasses several fundamental elements that serve as cornerstones for sound HRM policies. These include mentoring, managerial coaching, cross-training, career development and compensation. The work laid emphasis on Human Resource Development. According to Vulpen, (2016), human resource development develops the key competencies that enable individuals in organizations to perform current and future jobs through planned learning activities. It is the integrated use of training, organization, and career development efforts to improve individual, group, and organizational effectiveness. It develops the competencies that academic staff need to perform the current jobs and prepares them for future roles through planned learning activities. Human resource development focuses on matching the needs of the individual and the organization. While choosing the right person for the job and then retaining them has always been the focus on the human resource department, the emphasis of human resource development is on motivating and developing academic staff.

Human resource development is a relatively novel field of functional practice and academic study. In last two decades, human resource development was the fastest growing area of management development,

due to the great interest of organizations in the face of intense competition and changes in the business environment (Kareem, 2017). Human resource development has progressed from the narrow concept of training into a more complex approach to learning and developing knowledge at the individual and organizational level (Mittal, 2013). The term human resource development was introduced by Nadler (2012), he described it as a set of related processes which are aimed at behavioral change. Human resource development practices are positivity related to high performing business organizations. But there is a lack in empirical studies on human resource development in higher education. Mentoring, as a key component of human resource development, facilitates knowledge transfer, career growth, and professional competence, thereby strengthening the overall workforce capacity in public universities.

Mentoring is defined as a formal developmental relationship in which a more experienced academic provides guidance, advice, and support to a less experienced colleague to enhance personal and professional growth (Coetzee, Botha, Kiley & Truman, 2017). In university settings, mentoring is recognized as a strategic HRD practice that helps new and early-career academic staff integrate into institutional culture, improve teaching competence, and develop research capabilities (Coetzee et al., 2017). Research evidence indicates that structured mentoring programmes significantly improve academic staff performance outcomes by enhancing pedagogical effectiveness, promoting research productivity, and increasing job satisfaction (Malik & Nawaz, 2021; Mnasi, Matoka & Raphael, 2022). Mentoring also contributes to institutional capacity building by transmitting organizational knowledge, fostering collaborative research networks, and reinforcing competitive advantage (Njoku, 2018). Therefore, mentoring acts as an essential HRD mechanism that improves academic staff job performance in public universities by strengthening both professional competence and organizational commitment.

Mentoring has emerged as a strategic human resource development tool in public universities, significantly influencing academic staff job performance, motivation, and career progression. Numerous studies have emphasized that mentoring fosters knowledge sharing, improves job satisfaction, and enhances commitment to institutional goals. According to Eby et al. (2015), mentoring relationships within higher education institutions cultivate a supportive work environment where junior staff receive guidance, psychosocial support, and professional development opportunities. This support leads to improved job performance and reduced turnover intentions. Similarly, Dirani and Nafukho (2018) highlight that structured mentoring programs enable staff to align their personal career aspirations with institutional objectives, thereby fostering higher productivity and goal congruence. In the African context, Okurame and Balogun (2017) found that mentoring within public universities plays a crucial role in developing leadership capacity and academic excellence, particularly in resource-constrained environments where formal training opportunities are limited. Mentoring lays the foundation for managerial coaching by equipping academic staff with the skills and confidence needed to benefit from targeted leadership interventions.

Managerial coaching is defined as a developmental process in which supervisors or managers intentionally facilitate learning and performance improvement among subordinates through regular feedback, guidance, and support (Ellinger, Ellinger, Hamlin & Beattie, 2018). Managerial coaching occurs through ongoing interactions between academic supervisors, such as heads of departments or deans, and academic staff, with a focus on enhancing instructional skills, research oversight, and administrative effectiveness (Jones, Woods & Guillaume, 2019). This approach differs from traditional supervision by emphasizing support, dialogue, and collaborative problem solving rather than command-and-control practices (Boyatzis, Smith & Beveridge, 2019). Managerial coaching facilitates performance improvement by helping academic staff identify professional strengths, address performance gaps, and develop confidence in their roles (Kim, Eom, Kim & Youn, 2019). Regular coaching interactions have also been linked to increased job engagement, higher research output, and improved teaching effectiveness among faculty members (Muhlberger & Traut, 2019). Thus, managerial coaching serves as a critical HRD practice that enhances the job performance of academic staff in public universities.

Managerial coaching has increasingly been recognized as a key driver of academic staff job performance in public universities, serving as a personalized approach to performance enhancement and professional

growth. Unlike traditional supervisory methods, coaching by managers involves continuous feedback, collaborative goal setting, and the development of problem-solving skills. According to Ellinger et al. (2018), effective managerial coaching enhances academic staff self-efficacy and accountability, leading to increased productivity and engagement. In the context of public universities, where academic and administrative staff often face rigid bureaucracies and resource constraints, coaching creates a space for innovation and individualized support. Aslam et al. (2020) found that coaching positively affects performance by fostering a growth mindset and enabling staff to adapt to changing institutional demands. The study emphasized that coaching contributes to an environment of trust and open communication, which is essential for sustainable performance in higher education institutions.

In the twenty-first-century challenges such as globalization, technology, and demographic changes have forced the organizations to strive constantly searching for innovative ways to achieving the superior results in terms of efficiency and effectiveness and improving competitiveness with current academic staff. As a result, the concept of human resource development (HRD) has emerged as a strategy to improve the competence of the academic staff and for enhancement of organizational effectiveness. It is in this light that the researcher sought to investigate the impact of human resource development on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State.

Statement of the Problem

Academic staff job performance is widely regarded as a vital factor in achieving the goals of universities, particularly in the areas of teaching, research, and community service. However, there appear to be growing concerns that the level of job performance among some academic staff in public universities in Benue State may not be meeting the expected standards. Observations by stakeholders such as university administrators, government agencies and students seem to suggest that some lecturers might be experiencing challenges that could be affecting their productivity, research output, and commitment to academic responsibilities. This troubling situation may possibly be linked to weaknesses in human resource development practices within these universities. In particular, mentoring programmes that are expected to guide and support less experienced academic staff might not be adequately structured or consistently implemented, which could be limiting opportunities for knowledge transfer and professional growth.

Furthermore, managerial coaching, which is expected to provide guidance, feedback, and professional support to academic staff, appears to be insufficient or inconsistently practiced in some public universities in the state. It is possible that many academic staff rarely receive the necessary coaching from departmental heads or senior administrators that could enhance their teaching effectiveness and research productivity. Such a situation might contribute to low morale, reduced professional development, and declining academic performance if not properly addressed. Despite the importance of mentoring and managerial coaching in improving staff performance, it remains uncertain whether these human resource development strategies significantly influence academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State. This worrisome uncertainty therefore necessitated the need to investigate the impact of human resource development on academic staff job performance in the universities.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate impact of human resource development on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the impact of mentoring on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State.
2. ascertain the impact of managerial coaching on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study

1. What is the impact of mentoring on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State?

2. What is the impact of managerial coaching on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. Mentoring has no significant impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State.
2. Managerial coaching has no significant impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design for the study was ex-post facto survey. The population of the study comprised 2,042 academic staff in three public universities in Benue State. The sample was 355 academic staff representing 17.38% of the population and 343 questionnaire were returned answered. A researcher-developed questionnaire titled ““Human Resource Development and Academic Staff Job Performance Questionnaire (HRDASJPQ)” was administered to gather data. The reliability of the instrument was ascertained through a trial-test which yielded a Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.91. Data were analysed using Mean and Standard Deviation (σ) to answer research questions and Chi-square (χ^2) goodness-of-fit to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

A total of 355 copies of questionnaire were taken to the field and administered on respondents and 343 copies representing 97% of the questionnaire was returned answered and 12 copies representing 3% were damage or lost. The data presentation, analysis and interpretation for this study were based on the responses obtained from respondents on the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1: *What is the impact of mentoring on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Impact of Mentoring on Academic Staff Job Performance in Public Universities in Benue State

I/NO	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	σ	Decision
1	I perform better in my teaching responsibilities when I receive regular guidance from my senior colleague.	105	156	61	21	3.00	0.85	Agree
2	I am confident in performing my supervisory duties due to the advice I receive from senior colleagues.	130	97	91	25	2.96	0.96	Agree
3	I struggle to meet expectations without advice from experienced senior colleagues.	116	157	40	30	3.04	0.89	Agree
4	I find it difficult to perform my teaching duties due to the absence of experienced senior colleagues.	118	153	46	26	3.05	0.88	Agree
5	I am able to mark examination questions without any challenge due to the guidance I receive from my mentor.	91	157	25	70	2.78	1.05	Agree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation						2.96	0.92	Agree

Source: Field work 2026

Table 1 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents’ responses for items 1 to 5 are 3.00, 2.96, 3.04, 3.05 and 2.78 with corresponding standard deviations of 0.85, 0.96, 0.89, 0.88 and 1.05 respectively. The result indicates that the respondents largely agreed that regular guidance from senior colleagues enhances

academic staff performance in teaching responsibilities. Mentoring boost confidence in carrying out supervisory duties, suggesting that advice from experienced colleagues strengthens professional competence. Additionally, respondents agreed that the absence of advice from senior colleagues makes it difficult to meet expected academic standards, highlighting the supportive role mentoring plays in job performance. Furthermore, the findings revealed that lack of experienced senior colleagues negatively affects teaching effectiveness, implying that mentoring contributes significantly to instructional efficiency. However, guidance from mentors reduce challenges associated with marking examination scripts, indicating that mentoring supports accuracy and confidence in assessment practices. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 benchmark. The cluster mean of 2.96 was also above the benchmark of 2.50. This implies that mentoring has positive impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State.

Research Question 2: *What is the impact of managerial coaching on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Impact of Managerial Coaching on Academic Staff Job Performance in Public Universities in Benue State

I/NO	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	σ	Decision
6	I perform better in the supervision of students' project when I received regular feedback from my mentor.	132	107	56	48	2.94	1.05	Agree
7	I perform better in the screening of newly admitted students when my mentor gives me direction.	135	63	94	51	2.82	1.11	Agree
8	With the coaching I receive from my senior colleagues, it makes me more effective in supervision of students writing projects.	136	130	37	40	3.05	0.98	Agree
9	I am able to use appropriate teaching method because of personalized coaching.	121	112	64	46	2.89	1.03	Agree
10	I am more confident in handling administrative duties because of the coaching I have received from university leadership.	140	117	56	30	3.07	0.95	Agree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation						2.95	1.02	Agree

Source: Field work 2026

Table 2 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 6 to 10 are 2.94, 2.82, 3.05, 2.89 and 3.07 with corresponding standard deviations of 1.05, 1.11, 0.98, 1.03 and 0.95 respectively. The result indicates that the respondents largely agreed that regular feedback received through managerial coaching enhances academic staff performance in supervising students' projects. Managerial coaching also improves effectiveness in the screening of newly admitted students, suggesting that guidance from mentors supports accuracy and professionalism in admission-related responsibilities. Respondents agreed that coaching from senior colleagues enhances effectiveness in supervising students' project writing, indicating that managerial coaching strengthens supervisory competence. Furthermore, personalized coaching enable academic staff to adopt appropriate teaching methods, thereby improving instructional delivery. The findings also revealed that coaching from university leadership boosts confidence in handling administrative duties, suggesting that managerial coaching contributes to overall job effectiveness. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 benchmark. The cluster mean of 2.95 was also

above the benchmark of 2.50. This implies that managerial coaching has positive impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State.

Hypotheses Testing

In testing the hypotheses of this study, Chi-square (χ^2) test of goodness of fit was used to test the responses of respondents at .05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1: Mentoring has no significant impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State.

Table 3: Chi-square Test of Impact of Mentoring on Academic Staff Job Performance in Public Universities in Benue State

Response	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	df.	Level of sign.	χ^2	P-value	Decision
			3	0.05	570.688	.000	Sig.
SA	112	85.75					
A	144	85.75					
D	53	85.75					
SD	34	85.75					
Total	343						

Table 3 reveals that $\chi^2 = 570.688^a$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that mentoring has no significant impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State was therefore, rejected. This implies that mentoring has significant positive impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State.

Hypothesis 2: Managerial coaching has no significant impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State.

Table 4: Chi-square Test of Impact of Managerial Coaching on Academic Staff Job Performance in Public Universities in Benue State

Response	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	df.	Level of sign.	χ^2	P-value	Decision
			3	0.05	502.076	.000	Sig.
SA	133	85.75					
A	106	85.75					
D	61	85.75					
SD	43	85.75					
Total	343						

Table 4 reveals that $\chi^2 = 502.076^a$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degrees of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that managerial coaching has no significant impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State was therefore, rejected. This implies that managerial coaching has significant positive impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The following discussions of findings are presented based on the results obtained from the analyses of the hypotheses:

The first finding of the study showed that mentoring has positive significant impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State. This finding is in line with the findings of Adeniyi,

Tende and Emmanuel (2024) who revealed that mentoring significantly enhances academic staff job performance in public universities through continuous guidance, professional support, and knowledge sharing between senior and junior staff. The finding also agrees with the findings of Chika, Samuel and Azubuiké (2021) who found that mentoring positively influences academic staff effectiveness in teaching, supervision and research activities in Nigerian universities. The researcher also agrees with this finding that mentoring has positive significant impact on academic staff job performance. This is because effective mentoring enables academic staff to acquire professional skills, gain confidence in task execution and improve overall performance through sustained interaction with experienced colleagues in public universities.

The second finding of the study revealed that managerial coaching has positive significant impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State. This finding is consistent with the findings of Musa (2023) who found that managerial coaching improves academic staff productivity, instructional effectiveness and administrative competence in public universities. The finding also aligns with the findings of Okon (2022) who showed that coaching by university management enhances staff confidence, decision-making ability and overall job performance. The researcher also agrees with this finding that managerial coaching positively influences academic staff job performance. This is because regular coaching provides feedback, clarifies expectations and supports academic staff in developing skills required for effective teaching, supervision and administrative responsibilities in public universities.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that human resource development has significant positive significant impact on academic staff job performance in public universities in Benue State. Specifically, strategies such as mentoring, managerial coaching, cross-training, career development and compensation enhance teaching effectiveness, supervisory competence, administrative efficiency and overall work performance of academic staff. The findings revealed that when academic staff are provided with continuous guidance, professional support, opportunities to acquire new skills, career growth initiatives and fair rewards, their motivation, confidence and productivity are significantly improved. Therefore, human resource development serves as a critical factor in strengthening the capacity of academic staff to perform their duties effectively and contribute meaningfully to the achievement of institutional goals in public universities in Benue State.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The National Universities Commission should prioritize the implementation and support of structured mentoring programmes in public universities, recognizing that mentoring has a significant positive impact on academic staff job performance by enhancing teaching effectiveness, research output, and supervisory competence.
2. Educational planners should incorporate managerial coaching into staff development strategies, as the study shows that managerial coaching positively influences academic staff productivity, decision-making and administrative efficiency, thereby ensuring that universities are staffed with competent and confident personnel.

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